

Pest management and control INSECTS

Planting time and stem borer incidence in Badeggi, Nigeria

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We measured rice stem borer (SB) incidence on susceptible variety FARO 11 in 1981 and 1982 at the Badeggi RRS. FARO 11 was transplanted on d 12 or 13 of each month in 5 × 5-m plots, at 20 × 20-cm spacing, in 4 replications. SB incidence was recorded as the number of damaged stems to total tillers by dissecting 10 hills from each plot at 10-d intervals, from transplanting to harvest.

Results (see figure) showed that SB infestation was high for crops planted in Feb, Mar, and Apr and low for the Aug crop, in 1981. In 1982, SB incidence was high in Feb, Apr, and May crops and low

Stem borer incidence in different months in Badeggi, Nigeria.

for the Aug crop. Insect buildup begins in the wet season (Jun-Oct) and reaches its peak during dry season (Nov-May).

The insects of major importance were *Maliarpha separata* Ragonot (about 70% of total borers collected) and *Chilo* spp. □

Biology of the white leafhopper on rice

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The white leafhopper (WL) *Cofana spectra* (Distant) is becoming an important rice pest in Tamil Nadu. It causes stunting and yellowing of plants, and severe infestations cause plant death. We studied the biology of *C. spectra* at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, on potted TN1 rice plants. An average of 50 insects were observed for each parameter. The findings are summarized in the table.

Biology of *Cofana spectra* on rice, Coimbatore, India.

	Max	Min	Mean	S. D.
Egg				
Length (mm)	1.29	1.07	1.19	0.07
Width (mm)	0.39	0.31	0.35	0.01
No./cluster	19.0	5	10.84	3.46
Period (d)	10.0	9.5	9.6	0.27
Nymphal duration (d)				
Stage 1	9.0	7.0	8.4	0.81
Stage 2	6.0	3.0	4.7	0.73
Stage 3	7.0	4.0	5.4	0.75
Stage 4	8	5.0	6.7	1.18
Stage 5	3	1.0	2.7	0.66
Total	33	25.0	27.5	1.93
Sex ratio (female:male)	—	—	1:0.99	—
Fecundity (no. of eggs laid)	52	36	43.8	5.16
Adult longevity (d)				
Female	13	8	10.5	1.46
Male	9	5	7.1	1.19

Stenchaetothrips biformis (Bagnall): correct name for rice thrips

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Rice thrips, a serious pest of young rice plants, is often referred to by incorrect

names. Recent literature has used *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall).

Two leading authorities on world Thysanoptera, Bhatti and Mound (1980, Bull. Ent., 21:1-22), have transferred *biformis* to the genus *Stenchaetothrips* and used that genus in subsequent publications. *Stenchaetothrips biformis*

(Bagnall) is the correct name for rice thrips. Frequently used names for rice thrips such as *Bagnallia bifomis* Bagnall, *Thrips oryzae* Williams, *Thrips holophnus* Karny, *Chloethrips blandus* zur Strassen, and *Thrips dobrogensis* Knechtlet should not be used. □